

The Effect of Positive Asset Search in the Reflected Feelings and Needs among Individuals Who Lack Vision

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Abstract:- This study aimed to determine the effect of positive asset search as a counseling skill in the reflected feelings, reflected needs and basic emotions among visually impaired students. The aim of this study was to determine the number and types of reflected feelings and needs among visually impaired students. This study also tries to determine the difference in the feelings, needs and basic emotions among visually impaired and non-visually impaired students and to determine the effect of positive asset search intervention in the reflected feelings, reflected needs and basic emotions among visually impaired and non-visually impaired students. This study used a 4-group pre- posttest experimental research design, with visually impaired and non-visually impaired group of participants in both experimental and control group. All the dependent variables were measured initially with the participants and they were categorized into different groups based on certain criteria. The positive asset search intervention was given and the dependent variables were measured again to find out the difference. The results of this study showed that the positive asset search intervention was found to enhance the positive reflected feelings and positive emotions, by reducing negative reflected feelings and negative emotions among both visually impaired and non-visually impaired participants even though there was a slight variation on the effect of the intervention among the groups. There was no significant difference found among the control group and enhance the effect of positive asset search intervention could be validated.

I. INTRODUCTION

Counseling is known to be an art and science, interpersonal theory-based supporting service. The basic aim of counseling resolves the developmental and situational difficulties to modify life, thought, emotion and behaviour. 'A professional counsellor is meant to have a specialization in counselling with a master's or doctorate', as mentioned by, Witmer and Loesch, (1986). Counsellors should have basic skills of empathy, maturity, and warmth. In general, counseling is found to be an active process that differs largely from passively listening or attending to problems. The counselling process deals with various personal, social, educational, and vocational issues and decisions, which are mentioned in the American Counseling Association codes. Counseling could be best used for the individuals who were stuck and not sick with the psychological aspects. 'Counseling technique is considered as a process in which

the individuals learn to make new ways of thinking, feeling, and reacting, which consists of both choice and change, evolving through distinct stages such as exploration, goal setting, and action', which is mentioned by Brammer and Egan, (1990).

In the process of counselling, counselling skills refer to the interpersonal and technical traits that a counsellor uses to better understand and listen to their client. These skills help to build rapport, establish trust and ensure that the clients are being heard or understood, which involves, listening, silence, encouragement, self-awareness, self-disclosure, reflective skills, summarizing skills questioning skills, active observation, positive asset search, eye contact, body language, patience, facial expressions, and communication skills.

Researches in Counseling techniques created its wide expansion in most fields including, education, career, relationship, child development, family, marriage, and so on. The Counseling technique and its application are widely studied across different sectors. Augustino in 2018 conducted a study on the skills in the counseling technique widely, consisting of a study on the effectiveness of counseling skill training showed the incorporation of different skill training in counseling including reflection, encouragement, and immediacy. The study conducted by Erlina et al (2018) aimed at finding out the basic skills possessed by counselor candidates during the counseling session which showed the basic competence and the predominant importance of the basic counseling skills while conducting the session. There was a research gap found among the literature emphasizing specifically to assess the effect of each counseling skill on the clients. The study was hence formulated to assess the effect of a counseling skill on the client's feelings and emotions. Counseling techniques are guided by ethical and legal standards and go through distinct stages from initiation to termination. Behavioral change is a necessary result of the counselling process, although unique behaviors have little emphasis during the counselling experience (Roger 1961).

The application and development of the counselling process are widely studied and the wholistic application of the counselling skills was given more emphasis, still, the extent of application of each of the counselling skills is not given much importance based on the review of the literature. Among those skills, a positive asset search is found to be an important skill that was found to have a greater influence on the cognition and perception of the clients based on previous

experiences. The technique of counselling and counsellors training module could be developed and framed much more effectively if each of these counselling skills were thoroughly studied.

The positive search approach was found to have a significant influence on various therapeutic techniques. 'The Incorporation of a strength or positive search perspective in counselling is thought to prevent problems, promote human growth and maximize human potentiality' as mentioned by, Geilo and Fretz, (2001).

The positive assets, including the strengths and qualities of an individual, tend to be found hidden within, as when it is brought to the awareness of an individual would bring out a difference in the cognition and feelings of that individual. The positive asset search is all about bringing out the positive qualities of that individual to notice. The research on the integration of psychological interventions and skills on pediatric oncology by Karajan and Noll (2015), showed the influence of interventions to reduce the psychological effect of oncology made a specific significance on the motivation involved in reducing the intensity of the psychological impact of childhood cancer. The positive asset search among the individual was found to be an important factor in motivation. The theoretical inspiration and empirical direction in rehabilitation psychology by Dunn and Wegener (2016), showed that the application of positive asset search among the disabled during their rehabilitation was found to have a significant influence.

Researches were highly investigated on the strength and positive assets approach towards resolving various issues of the clients with their cooperation and acceptance of the therapeutic interventions according Seaman et al (1999). Yue incorporation of client's strength approach began from the three basic sources which includes Gelso's (2003), usage of client's strength in psychotherapies, second one is Seligman's (1999), approach to positive psychology which tries to understand in developing the qualities and strengths, third emphasizing on optimal human functioning, and the third is the constructivist approach which focuses on construction of client's strength making them efficient enough to resolve their own issues. The positive assets in the therapeutic with attention to client's strengths and assets was thus be found to be an important and potential that yet needs to be explored deeper into.

The emotion, feelings and its expression as explained by Caroli, 2009 is a complex combination of cognition, behavioural and physiological functions. Emotions were found to be a functional aspect of the neurons and the body parts. The responses towards internal and external stimulus through feelings begins from birth itself. During childhood, the emotional responses are observed as involuntary natural reflexes towards stimulus. Based on free flow of responses and sympathy. Small children expresses emotions without thinking about it, but grown up and matured were supposed to express and reacts based on the stimulus more voluntarily and appropriately according to the human civilization and culture, The expression of consequential emotion towards

stimulus or situation among small children without considering the social code of conduct was found to be normal, but if the same happens with grown up or matured ones, it would be considered psychological abnormality. For the normal socio psychological development on an individual, it is important to attain the emotional stability and responses as per the social code of conduct with the development of emotional intelligence and emotional competence. Emotion competency is defined as the ability to understand, learn, reflect and express emotions based on the social code of conduct in an appropriate way without psychological stress to themselves or others. It was observed that emotion play a direct role influencing the thoughts, interpretation and actions of individuals. An imbalance in the emotional states and its regulation can further interferes with the thinking, perception and overall wellbeing of their personal and social life. Negative emotions were found to trigger harmful chemicals and neurotransmitters such as cortisol which could have an altering effect on the physiological and psychological states unlike the positive emotions which relatively balances and triggers useful chemicals and neurotransmitters such as dopamine which are non toxic in nature.

From the works in the existence of basic primary emotions dates back from the works of Descartes (1649/1988), who states all the emotions were derived from the six fundamental emotions such as joy, sadness, love, hatred, desire and wonder, however the the investigation on the basic fundamental emotions basically started from the publication of Darwin's (1872/1998) book on 'The Expression of Emotions on Man and Animals'. The cruciality of emotions and its importance in likelihood were also explained by Darwin. It further leads to the identification that some emotions are innate being universal which is hard wired in all brains such as fear, sadness, pleasure etc. Ekman further developed and published the existence of six fundamental emotions consisting of, happiness, sadness, anger, fear, excitement, and disgust who further published a visual analog scale of the six basic emotions.

A staggering 2.2 billion individuals worldwide have some form of visual impairment, of whom 36 million are blind, while an estimated 217 million have been diagnosed with partial blindness. A primary contributor to impairment among the elderly in the United States is age-related vision loss brought on by ageing, which is mostly caused by eye conditions such macular degeneration, cataracts, glaucoma, and diabetic retinopathy. The prevalence of moderate to severe vision impairment is predicted to rise over the next 30 years. Therefore, it is necessary to have a thorough grasp of the numerous implications that vision impairments have on a person's psychological health, quality of life, and general well-being is required (Docia and Stevenson, 2019).

Camano and his colleagues (2013), assessed sportive and non-sportive visually impaired subjects on their psychological wellbeing and social participation. The purpose of this study was to assess the differences in psychological well-being, symptomatic psychological disorders and social participation. Among the two subject

groups, a correlation between well-being and social skills was found. Furthermore, sportive visually impaired subjects had greater levels of wellbeing and sociability characteristics.

In a 1989 study on the education of blind and visually impaired children in India, T. B. Sing presented various approaches to inclusive and special education for the visually impaired. It had a tremendous impact on enhancing the blind and visually impaired population's educational system and expanding their opportunities and skill sets through targeted initiatives.

Vision loss is an important cause of the gradual economic burden and the over-dependency of that individual on others, which was found to gradually reduce the quality of their life and standard. The visual impairment was also found to have a significant influence on the psychological well-being of the individual due to their reduced ability and sense of dependence resulting in an inferiority complex and a sense of economic burden. Visual impairment is generally considered a physical problem due to the improper functioning of the eyes, but it had a significant impact on their psychological state as well which is mostly unnoticed or underrecognized.

The study about reflective practices has been vibrantly dynamic and adaptable with its reflective competencies & skills under various Clinical Psychology Courses being promoted lately as noted by Brown in 2009. Although, its impact also has been vital to trainees & other practitioners, exhibited by Knight et al in 2010; the missing subjective nature on the various aspect and dimensions of the same is questionable. As observed by Neal, Wigg & Cushway in 2011, the positive response to reflective practice has been displayed while focus on methodology and insight on how the reflective practice is helpful isn't signified in results.

The feelings expressed by one and its interpretation by the observer can be understood through reflection of feelings. Ochsner et al. (2004) studied neural systems supporting the attributions of emotions on reflection of feelings through fMRI. The study showed that the brain regions like medial prefrontal cortex, the superior temporal gyrus, and posterior cingulate gets activated while judging one's own emotions and experiencing another individual's emotions. This indicated the similar influence of emotional reaction to both self and others among individuals. Another study (Mortan, 2015) aimed to reflect on emotional experience based on emotion and education, resulted that the application and concept of effective self-understanding played as significant factor in the reflection of emotions by the individuals.

The study conducted by Ann M G et al (2016), on special needs as an ineffective euphemism, showed the usage of certain terms to reduce the intensity of differences among the disabled and their requirements was found to be relatively more negativistic than directly depicting those needs. The study on the needs of expressed emotions of parents of children with developmental disabilities by Coleman and Olmos (2018), which shows a significantly high rate of expressed emotions among the parents of children with

developmental disorders. A study conducted by MacIver et al (2018), on the need for participation of children with disabilities in school, showed the three overarching mechanisms representing psychosocial factors for children which include, identity, competence, and experience of mind and body. It also figured out the basic five environmental aspects affecting the improved children's participation at school.

The basic emotions expressed feelings, and needs are some of the most common observable factors in therapy to determine its effectiveness. There were several types of research focusing on the application and effectiveness of counseling and therapies among various groups of individuals and its developments are widely focused. The studies also made a note on the different counseling skills and their necessities during a counseling session, but there was a research gap found among the assessment of each of the counseling skills and its effect on an individual. A positive asset search is noted as one of the important counseling skills based on motivational therapy as stated by Murayama in 2018.

The study on special needs as an ineffective understatement, conducted by Ann M G et al (2016) revealed that the use of specific phrases to decrease the intensity of diversity among the disabled and their requirements was shown to be comparatively more negativistic than directly presenting those needs. Coleman and Olmos (2018) conducted a study on the expressed emotion demands of parents of children with developmental impairments, which revealed A wide range of researches on the application of counselling in rehabilitation and among individuals with disabilities were conducted, but these studies could only provide with indication of low importance in developing a unique counselling strategy for individuals with disability as their way of perceiving things has a wide difference due to their differences in adaptation. Visual senses is one of the most important and basic sense of a human for perceiving and understanding the world around him. As viewed in this context, there is much more emphasis to be given for those with visual impairment among these studies. As per the research findings it is revealed that loss of vision makes one more dependent in their day to day living and this dependency makes them more vulnerable to psychological distress.

Thus the present study sets out to explore the effect of positive asset search on the feelings, needs, basic emotions and need efficacy of individuals with visual impairment. The study also try to find out whether there is any difference in the range of effects of positive asset search among individuals with vision and those who are visually impaired. Thus the current study could also be a basis for developing a new therapy for individuals with visual impairment.

II. METHOD

➤ Aim

This study aims to determine the changes in the reflective feelings, reflective needs and basic emotions with the counseling skill of positive asset search during counseling among visually impaired students.

➤ Objectives

- To identify the nature and number of feelings and needs among individuals with vision lose and with normal vision.
- To assess the level of feelings, needs, and basic emotions among individuals with vision lose and with normal vision.
- To study_the_difference in the reflective feelings, reflective needs, need efficacy, basic emotions, and participant satisfaction among individuals with vision lose and with normal vision.
- To study the effect of Positive Asset Search in the reflected feelings and needs among individuals with vision lose and with normal vision.

III. RESEARCH DESIGN

An experimental research design is used in this study to evaluate the effect of positive asset search Intervention on the Reflective feelings, Reflective needs, Need efficacy, basic emotions, and Client satisfaction among the participants. The manipulated variable taken by the researcher is positive asset search. A quantitative method of data analysis is to be used in this study to compare and analyze the Reflective feelings, Reflective needs, Need efficacy, Basic emotions, and Client satisfaction among the participants.

A comparative research technique is used in this study to see the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variables among the experimental group. Also, the dependent variables are to be compared among two independent groups.

This study uses the initial storytelling part in Eagan's skilled helper model in counseling, which consists of the rapport formation stage, storytelling stage, challenging stage with positive asset search intervention, and finally the re-story telling stage. The independent variable was taken to be the positive asset search intervention with the dependent variables of reflective feeling, reflective needs and basic emotions.

The convenient sampling technique was used for this study and the sample size is fixed to be 64, where 31 with visual impairment and 33 are without any visual impairment.

➤ Procedure

The data for this study was collected from visually impaired individuals and a comparable group of individuals with vision belonging to the age group of 14 to 25 from Kerala. The participants who are visually impaired was selected by reaching onto the Kerala Federation for Blind, RCG foundation, and the Kerala branch of the National Federation for Blind. The comparable group of participants with vision would be selected in comparison to the age group,

socio-economic status, education, and location of the participants with visual impairment. This study could be conducted in 10 stages. It started with the collection of pre test data after getting the consent from the organizaations and individuals through a story telling phase. The implementation of the positive assets search is conducted as the following step with collection of post test data through a restory telling phase.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data for the study was collected from 64 participants with 31 visually impaired and 33 non visually impaired participants. The 64 participants were categorized into the experimental group in which the 31 visually impaired participants were classified into experimental group 1 and the 33 non visually impaired participants were classified into experimental group 2. Among the participants, 21 participants were categorized into the delayed experimental group which consists of 10 visually impaired participants classified into the control group 1 and 11 non visually impaired participants categorized into control group 2. The visually impaired participants were selected from Palakkad, Thrissur, Ernakulam, Thiruvananthapuram, Malappuram, Kannur and Kalakoda districts of Kerala state from the Kerala Federation of Blinds, Kerala branch of National Federation of Blinds and RCG foundation from Enable India. The non-visually impaired participants were selected from the respective educational institutes of the visually impaired from the same location.

This study aimed to determine the difference in the reflected feelings, reflected needs, and basic emotions among the visually impaired students as a result of the positive asset search intervention. The sample was considered to be visually impaired because the existing research showed that vision loss is an important predictor of excessive dependence and emotional breakdowns. The study also tried to compare if there was any significant difference in the range of basic emotions, positive feelings, and negative feelings among the visually impaired in comparison to the non-visually impaired, by determining the extent of the effect of positive asset search. The study fixed the population to be the visually impaired belonging to the age group of 14 to 25 from, KFB, NFB, and RCG foundation based on Kerala origin. The sampling technique used was the availability sampling technique. 31 visually impaired participants were selected for this study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. A total number of 33 non visually impaired participants having a comparable age group, socioeconomic status, family, and same school were collected for making the comparison and to determine the effect of the positive asset search intervention. The control group consists of 10 visually impaired and 11 non visually impaired students. An experimental 2-group pre-post research design is used in this study. The first independent t-test was done among the experimental and control group before the positive asset search to check if there was any significant difference in the dependent variables between the experimental and the control group before the intervention. By the next stage, the visually impaired and non-visually impaired before the intervention was compared to see if there

was any significant difference among the dependent variables. In the third part, the control group data during observation 1 and observation 2 was compared using the dependent t-test to check if there was any significant difference in any dependent variables due to the extraneous variables. The experimental group before and after the positive asset search intervention was then compared using the dependent t-test to check if there was any significant difference in the dependent variables before and after the intervention. The pre and post-test difference scores among the experimental and the control group were compared using the independent t-test to check if there was any significant difference in the dependent variables based on the difference scores. In the next step, the experimental and control group in observation 2 was compared using the independent t-test if there was any significant difference found among the dependent variables after the intervention. Finally, the visually impaired and non-visually impaired participant scores after the intervention were compared using the independent t-test to see if there was any significant difference between the visually impaired and non-visually impaired after the positive asset search intervention.

Table 4.1 showed that there was an increase in the mean scores of the visually impaired and non-visually impaired experimental group after the positive asset search intervention. It was found that the variation of the mean scores in the control group after the positive asset search intervention was also found to have some variation which was found to be inconsistent as the mean scores among the control group after the intervention was found to have decreased and among the non-visually impaired was slightly increased. This could show that the time gap would bring about a variation in the number of positive feeling words among the participant might be based on the situation. Even then it could be validated that the positive asset search intervention could bring about a consistent enhancement in the number of positive feelings among both visually impaired and non-visually impaired. There was a decrease in the mean scores in negative feeling words among the visually impaired and non-visually impaired experimental group in the number of negative feeling words. There was no observable variation in the number of negative feeling words mean scores observed among the control group, which showed that the decrease in the number of negative feeling words could be a result of the positive asset search intervention. There was an increase in the frequency, intensity, and positive feelings as well as the range of happiness among the visually impaired and non-visually impaired experimental group. There were some slight variations in the frequency, intensity, and strength of the control group after the intervention which was inconsistent and fluctuating.

There was a consistent decrease in the frequency, intensity, and strength of negative feeling words along with the range of sadness and anger among the visually impaired and non-visually impaired experimental group after the positive asset search intervention. There were some variations in the mean scores in frequency, intensity, and strength of positive feeling words, range of sadness, and anger among the control group also which were found to be fluctuating. It

might be because of the change in situation and background influencing the negative emotions. The consistent decrease in the negative emotions among the experimental group after the positive asset search intervention could show the effect of the intervention in reducing the effect of negative feelings.

There were slight variations in the number of needs, frequency, intensity, strength, and need efficacy among the visually impaired and non-visually impaired participants in the experimental group. of need and the control group. The difference was found to be highly fluctuating and hence could be denoted that there was no significant difference found as a result of the positive asset search intervention.

Research on motivational interviewing interviews defines that there was a significant effect of motivational interviewing on the current emotional states of the participant. It was also found that there was no consistent difference in the range of basic emotions, positive and negative feelings among the control group, before and after the positive asset search intervention on visually impaired and non-visually impaired. The study entitled 'Beyond the Cognition, Broadening the Emotional Base of Motivational Interviewing', (Christopher et al, 2017), showed evidence that motivational interviewing was closely associated with the positive asset search in modifying and altering the emotional base and reactivity and enhancing the positive affect among the clients. This study supports the evidence for the enhancement in the scores of the components of positive feelings after the positive asset search intervention. The study conducted by Antonia in 2015 on Positive Motivational Interviewing as a component for activating a client's strengths and intrinsic motivation to change, showed a direct correlation between the effect of motivational interviewing and positive asset search as comparable.

The independent t-test results among the experimental and control group on visually impaired and non-visually impaired before the intervention was given in table 4.2. The independent t-test among the experimental and the control group was done before the intervention in order to check if there was any significant difference in the reflected feelings and reflected needs and basic emotions before the intervention. The t-test results showed that there was no significant difference in any of the dependent variables at 0.01 level of depicting 99% of confidence stating the significant difference. The number, frequency and intensity of positive feelings were found to be relatively similar among the experimental and the control group on visually impaired and non-visually impaired.

The results shown on the independent t-test among the visually impaired before the intervention shows a significant difference in the positive strength and number of needs among the experimental and control group at 0.05 level of significance, depicting 95% of confidence. This could be because of the relatively a smaller number of samples depicting the control group when compared to the experimental group and the standard deviation on positive feeling strength and number of needs was found to be large. The significant difference in the positive feeling strength and

number of needs among the experimental and control group could also be because of the limited number of exclusion criteria used in this study as some of those factors could also lead to a significant difference among the experimental and control group before the intervention.

There was no significant difference found in the number, frequency and intensity of both positive and negative feeling among the experimental and the control group. Also, there was no significant difference found in the frequency, intensity, strength and efficacy of needs along with the 6 basic emotions. It thus showed that the experimental group and the control group were comparable in terms of needs, feelings and basic emotions even though there was a heterogeneity with the number of participants in the experimental and control group.

The independent t-test was performed among the visually impaired and non-visually impaired participants before the intervention to check if there was any significant difference among the dependent variables. The results obtained and mentioned in table 4.3, showed that, there was no significant difference at 0.01 level of significance depicting 99% of confidence level among any of the dependent variables. This showed that the reflected feelings, needs and basic emotions were not found to be significantly different among the visually impaired and non-visually impaired participants. This showed that there was no higher degree of variations in the feelings, needs and basic emotions among the visually impaired and non-visually impaired participants in this study.

Among the 64 participants belonging to the experimental group on both visually impaired and non-visually impaired showed a significant difference in the need frequency at 0.05 level of significance showing 95% of confidence level...This could be because of the reason that there was a significant difference in the frequency of expressed needs among the visually impaired and non-visually impaired. The mean scores showed that the need frequency was found to be more in case of non-visually impaired participants belonging to the experimental group before the intervention. It was also found that among the control group before the intervention, there was a significant difference found at 0.05 level of significance in the dependent variables of positive feeling frequency, negative feeling intensity, negative feeling strength, need intensity and need strength, among visually impaired and non-visually impaired participants. This showed that the feelings and needs of the visually impaired and non-visually impaired showed a significant difference among the control group and one of the reasons could be because of the relatively fewer number of sample size representative of the control group with 10 visually impaired and 11 non visually impaired. It could be as though interpreted that there was a slight variation and difference in the feelings and needs among visually impaired and non-visually impaired, but it was not to be considered as significant.

There was no significant difference found among the dependent variables of feelings, dimensions of needs and basic emotions except number of needs among the experimental group before the intervention among visually impaired and non-visually impaired. There was no significant difference found in the dependent variables of number of positive feelings, number of negative feelings, intensity of positive feeling, strength of positive feeling, frequency of negative feeling, number, frequency, intensity and strength of needs along with the need efficacy and 6 basic emotions among the visually impaired and non-visually impaired participants in the control group, A comparative study conducted by Ravisankar and Brundha in 2016, on a comparison of touch perception in visually impaired and non-visually impaired showed evidences on sensory compensation hypothesis resulting in the variation and critical perceptual interpretation of individuals due to their vision lose transferring it to touch. Even though, in the current study, there was no significant variations of difference found among the basic emotions of the visually impaired and non-visually impaired participants.

The observation 1 and observation 2 scores of the control group were compared using the dependent t-test to check if there was any significant difference in the dependent variables which might be caused due to the extraneous factors to validate that the difference in the dependent variables happened as a result of the positive asset search intervention. The dependent t-test results in the control group before and after the intervention period showed that there was no significant difference found among the feelings, needs, and basic emotions at a 0.01 level of significance showing 99% of confidence. This showed that the feelings, needs, and basic emotions were not being changed or altered due to the influence of extraneous variables such as period, practice effect, etc.

Table 4.4 also showed that there were no dependent variables found to have a significant difference at a 0.05 level of significance with 95% of confidence. Research and theory state that the pattern of feelings, needs, and basic emotions remained to be quite constant, which showed that feelings, needs, and basic emotions could be influenced by situational factors, but a consistent pattern in modifying emotional and need interpretation requires consistent effort and practice.

The number, frequency, intensity, and strength of positive feelings, negative feelings, needs, need efficacy and the 6 basic emotions don't have a significant difference among the control group when compared among observation1 and observation 2. The feelings, needs, and basic emotions were found to have a greater influence over the day-to-day actions and quality of life of an individual (Mustapha, Ismail, and Dalshad, 2020). This also showed the importance and necessity of developing an intervention to enhance the range of basic emotions and positive feelings among an individual. The non-significant difference in the pre and post-test data among the control group validated the impact of the intervention in modifying the feelings, needs, and basic emotions among the participants.

V. TABLES

Table 4.1, Showing the Mean & SD of the visually impaired and nonvisual impaired, experimental and control group, before and after the intervention

SL. No	Variables	Visually Impaired				Non-Visually Impaired			
		Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		Post-test	
		Expt (N=31)	Control (N=10)	Expt (N=31)	Control (N=10)	Expt (N= 33)	Control (N= 11)	Expt (N= 33)	Control (N= 11)
		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
1	No, positive feeling	1.96 (.73)	1.80 (.69)	2.22 (.92)	1.41 (.82)	1.80 (.69)	2.11 (1.07)	1.87 (.99)	2.01 (1.00)
2	No, negative feeling	2.16 (.89)	2.21(1.45)	1.30 (.71)	2.20 (1.45)	2.21(1.45)	3.20 (1.3)	1.37 (.63)	3.20 (1.30)
3	Positive feeling frequency	4.67 (2.59)	3.5 (2.22)	7.22 (.42)	3.3 (1.8)	3.5 (2.22)	5.00 (2.74)	6.18 (.51)	5.1 (2.7)
4	Positive feeling intensity	9.80 (1.02)	9.6 (.76)	15.83 (1.15)	23.6 (4.68)	9.6 (.76)	14.7 (8.52)	13.03 (1.24)	14.4 (8.0)
5	Positive feeling strength	32.67 (3.39)	21.7 (1.91)	54.0 (3.296)	21.9 (1.95)	21.7 (1.91)	38.0 (2.2)	44.15 (1.91)	37.6 (2.29)
6	Negative feeling frequency	8.87 (.72)	8.9 (6.3)	5.19(.54)	8.9 (6.3)	8.9 (6.3)	12.6 (4.97)	5.33 (.43)	12.8 (4.77)
7	Negative feeling intensity	14.16 (1.03)	13.3 (8.06)	9.12 (.88)	13.0 (7.78)	13.3 (8.06)	22.0 (8.71)	9.21 (.78)	21.7 (8.09)
8	Negative feeling strength	58.17 (5.30)	50.6 (3.8)	32.12 (4.04)	50 (3.8)	50.6 (3.8)	91.3 (3.63)	35.39 (3.28)	90.8 (3.6)
9	No. needs	1.90 (.59)	2.3 (.48)	1.81 (.48)	2.0 (.47)	2.3 (.48)	2.2 (.78)	1.94 (.49)	2.2 (.63)
10	Need frequency	6.90 (.47)	7.6 (2.9)	6.87 (2.3)	7.0 (2.9)	7.6 (2.9)	10.2 (4.1)	7.90 (2.60)	9.3 (3.56)
11	Need intensity	12.67 (.75)	14.7 (4.1)	12.77 (3.45)	14.5 (4.14)	14.7 (4.1)	14.0 (5.52)	13.42 (3.59)	14.9 (5.38)
12	Need strength	46.67 (3.55)	49.5 (2.3)	49.48 (17.54)	49.6 (2.3)	49.5 (2.3)	69.7 (3.3)	55.33 (22.53)	69.7 (3.3)
13	Need efficacy	12.09 (.79)	12.3 (6.0)	13.48 (3.77)	11.6 (5.5)	12.3 (6.0)	13.1 (14.3)	14.18 (3.14)	12.7 (3.9)
14	Happy	3.03 (.65)	3.0 (.66)	3.64 (.48)	2.9 (.73)	3.0 (.66)	2.8 (.63)	3.3 (.79)	2.8 (.68)
15	Anger	3.30 (.81)	3.6(.69)	2.74 (.63)	3.5 (.52)	3.6(.69)	3.1 (.74)	2.64 (.64)	3.1 (.73)
16	Sad	3.09 (.82)	3.2 (.78)	2.47 (.62)	2.5 (.52)	3.2 (.78)	3.8 (.78)	2.89 (.63)	3.1 (.56)
17	Fear	2.98 (.97)	3.3 (1.05)	2.79 (.89)	3.3 (1.1)	3.3 (1.05)	2.5 (.71)	2.53 (.65)	2.5 (.71)
18	Excitement	3.22 (.91)	3.0 (.81)	3.27 (.87)	2.9 (.74)	3.0 (.81)	3.1 (.73)	2.85 (.93)	2.8 (.63)
19	Disgust	2.00 (.58)	2 (.47)	1.87 (.56)	2 (.47)	2 (.47)	2 (.47)	1.97 (.92)	2 (.47)
20	Participant Satisfaction			8.91 (.63)	5.2 (.91)			8.69 (.86)	4.1 (1.05)

Table 4.2, Showing the the t-test results of the Experimental group and Control group before the intervention in visually impaired and non-visually impaired

Sl. No	Variables	Visually impaired			Non-Visually Impaired		
		Expt (N= 31)	Control (N= 10)	t-value	Expt (N=33)	Control (N=11)	t-value
		Mean & SD	Mean & SD		Mean &SD	Mean &SD	
1	No, positive feeling	1.96 (.73)	1.80 (.69)	1.01	1.80 (.69)	2.11 (1.07)	.37
2	No, negative feeling	2.16 (.89)	2.21(1.45)	.12	2.21(1.45)	3.20 (1.3)	.23
3	Positive feeling frequency	4.67 (2.59)	3.5 (2.22)	1.29	3.5 (2.22)	5.00 (2.74)	.43
4	Positive feeling intensity	9.80 (1.02)	9.6 (.76)	.09	9.6 (.76)	14.7 (8.52)	.16
5	Positive feeling strength	32.67 (3.39)	21.7 (1.91)	1.69*	21.7 (1.91)	38.0 (2.2)	.46
6	Negative feeling frequency	8.87 (.72)	8.9 (6.3)	-0.17	8.9 (6.3)	12.6 (4.97)	.61
7	Negative feeling intensity	14.16 (1.03)	13.3 (8.06)	-.37	13.3 (8.06)	22.0 (8.71)	.29
8	Negative feeling strength	58.17 (5.30)	50.6 (3.8)	.65	50.6 (3.8)	91.3 (3.63)	1.54
9	No. needs	1.90 (.59)	2.3 (.48)	1.9*	2.3 (.48)	2.2 (.78)	.78
10	Need frequency	6.90 (.47)	7.6 (2.9)	.7	7.6 (2.9)	10.2 (4.1)	.59
11	Need intensity	12.67 (.75)	14.7 (4.1)	1.33	14.7 (4.1)	14.0 (5.52)	.49
12	Need strength	46.67 (3.55)	49.5 (2.3)	.39	49.5 (2.3)	69.7 (3.3)	1.22
13	Need efficacy	12.09 (.79)	12.3 (6.0)	.12	12.3 (6.0)	13.1 (14.3)	.31
14	Happy	3.03 (.65)	3.0 (.66)	.13	3.0 (.66)	2.8 (.63)	.78
15	Anger	3.30 (.81)	3.6(.69)	1.02	3.6(.69)	3.1 (.74)	.35
16	Sad	3.09 (.82)	3.2 (.78)	.35	3.2 (.78)	3.8 (.78)	.48
17	Fear	2.98 (.97)	3.3 (1.05)	.87	3.3 (1.05)	2.5 (.71)	.12
18	Excitement	3.22 (.91)	3.0 (.81)	.69	3.0 (.81)	3.1 (.73)	.01
19	Disgust	2.00 (.58)	2 (.47)	.01	2 (.47)	2 (.47)	.21

** - Showing the significant difference at 0.01 level

* - Showing significant difference at 0.05 level

Table 4.3 showing the independent t-test results of Visually impaired and non-visually impaired before the intervention

Sl. No	Variables	Experimental Group			Control Group		
		Visually Impaired (N= 31)	Non-Visually Impaired (N=33)	t-value	Visually Impaired (N=10)	Non-Visually Impaired (N=11)	t-value
		Mean & SD	Mean & SD		Mean & SD	Mean & SD	
1	No, positive feeling	1.96 (.73)	1.80 (.69)	.04	1.80 (.69)	2.11 (1.07)	1.40
2	No, negative feeling	2.16 (.89)	2.21(1.45)	.45	2.21(1.45)	3.20 (1.3)	1.27
3	Positive feeling frequency	4.67 (2.59)	3.5 (2.22)	.14	3.5 (2.22)	5.00 (2.74)	1.7*
4	Positive feeling intensity	9.80 (1.02)	9.6 (.76)	.40	9.6 (.76)	14.7 (8.52)	1.36
5	Positive feeling strength	32.67 (3.39)	21.7 (1.91)	.16	21.7 (1.91)	38.0 (2.2)	1.35
6	Negative feeling frequency	8.87 (.72)	8.9 (6.3)	.24	8.9 (6.3)	12.6 (4.97)	1.47
7	Negative feeling intensity	14.16 (1.03)	13.3 (8.06)	1.1	13.3 (8.06)	22.0 (8.71)	2.46*
8	Negative feeling strength	58.17 (5.30)	50.6 (3.8)	.96	50.6 (3.8)	91.3 (3.63)	1.85*
9	No. needs	1.90 (.59)	2.3 (.48)	.69	2.3 (.48)	2.2 (.78)	.42
10	Need frequency	6.90 (.47)	7.6 (2.9)	1.68*	7.6 (2.9)	10.2 (4.1)	.98
11	Need intensity	12.67 (.75)	14.7 (4.1)	.20	14.7 (4.1)	14.0 (5.52)	2.46*
12	Need strength	46.67 (3.55)	49.5 (2.3)	1.27	49.5 (2.3)	69.7 (3.3)	1.82*
13	Need efficacy	12.09 (.79)	12.3 (6.0)	.96	12.3 (6.0)	13.1 (14.3)	.42
14	Happy	3.03 (.65)	3.0 (.66)	.50	3.0 (.66)	2.8 (.63)	1.01
15	Anger	3.30 (.81)	3.6(.69)	.93	3.6(.69)	3.1 (.74)	.46
16	Sad	3.09 (.82)	3.2 (.78)	1.55	3.2 (.78)	3.8 (.78)	1.53

17	Fear	2.98 (.97)	3.3 (1.05)	1.48	3.3 (1.05)	2.5 (.71)	1.62
18	Excitement	3.22 (.91)	3.0 (.81)	.98	3.0 (.81)	3.1 (.73)	.01
19	Disgust	2.00 (.58)	2 (.47)	.15	2 (.47)	2 (.47)	.41

** - Showing the significant difference at 0.01 level

* - Showing significance at 0.05 level

Table 4.4, Showing the dependent t-test results of control group before and after the positive asset search intervention

Sl. No	Variables	Visually Impaired			Non-Visually Impaired		
		Pre (N=10)	Post (N=10)	t-value	Pre (N=11)	Post (N=11)	t-value
		Mean (SD)	Means		Means	Means	
1	No, positive feeling	1.80 (.69)	1.41 (.82)	.97	2.11 (1.07)	2.01 (1.00)	.01
2	No, negative feeling	2.21(1.45)	2.20 (1.45)	.32	3.20 (1.3)	3.20 (1.30)	.02
3	Positive feeling frequency	3.5 (2.22)	3.3 (1.8)	.51	5.00 (2.74)	5.1 (2.7)	.19
4	Positive feeling intensity	9.6 (.76)	23.6 (4.68)	.024	14.7 (8.52)	14.4 (8.0)	.51
5	Positive feeling strength	21.7 (1.91)	21.9 (1.95)	.32	38.0 (2.2)	37.6 (2.29)	.19
6	Negative feeling frequency	8.9 (6.3)	8.9 (6.3)	.01	12.6 (4.97)	12.8 (4.77)	.81
7	Negative feeling intensity	13.3 (8.06)	13.0 (7.78)	.63	22.0 (8.71)	21.7 (8.09)	.49
8	Negative feeling strength	50.6 (3.8)	0.5 (3.8)	.23	91.3 (3.63)	90.8 (3.6)	.72
9	No. needs	2.3 (.48)	2.0 (.47)	1.03	2.2 (.78)	2.2 (.63)	.65
10	Need frequency	7.6 (2.9)	7.0 (2.9)	1.20	10.2 (4.1)	9.3 (3.56)	.91
11	Need intensity	14.7 (4.1)	14.5 (4.14)	.83	14.0 (5.52)	14.9 (5.38)	1.03
12	Need strength	49.5 (2.3)	49.6 (2.3)	.24	69.7 (3.3)	69.7 (3.3)	1.3
13	Need efficacy	12.3 (6.0)	11.6 (5.5)	.87	13.1 (14.3)	12.7 (3.9)	.1
14	Happy	3.0 (.66)	2.9 (.73)	.53	2.8 (.63)	2.8 (.68)	.08
15	Anger	3.6(.69)	3.5 (.52)	.87	3.1 (.74)	3.1 (.73)	.21
16	Sad	3.2 (.78)	2.5 (.52)	1.02	3.8 (.78)	3.1 (.56)	.67
17	Fear	3.3 (1.05)	3.3 (1.1)	.21	2.5 (.71)	2.5 (.71)	.03
18	Excitement	3.0 (.81)	2.9 (.74)	.56	3.1 (.73)	2.8 (.63)	.21
19	Disgust	2 (.47)	2 (.47)	.42	2 (.47)	2 (.47)	.64

** - Showing the significance difference at 0.01 level

* - Showing the significance difference at 0.05 level

Table 4.5, Showing the dependent t-test results of experimental group on visually impaired and non-visually impaired, before and after positive asset search intervention

Sl. No	Variables	Visually Impaired			Non-Visually Impaired		
		Pre (N=31)	Post (N=31)	t-value	Pre (N=33)	Post (N=33)	t-value
		Mean & sd	Mean & sd		Mean & sd	Mean & sd	
1	No, positive feeling	1.96 (.73)	2.22 (.92)	4.86**	1.80 (.69)	1.87 (.99)	3.5**
2	No, negative feeling	2.16 (.89)	1.30 (.71)	4.73**	2.21(1.45)	1.37 (.63)	3.74**
3	Positive feeling frequency	4.67 (2.59)	7.22 (.42)	5.73**	3.5 (2.22)	6.18 (.51)	5.44**
4	Positive feeling intensity	9.80 (1.02)	15.83 (1.15)	4.74**	9.6 (.76)	13.03 (1.24)	3.63**
5	Positive feeling strength	32.67 (3.39)	54.0 (3.296)	6.51**	21.7 (1.91)	44.15 (1.91)	5.34**
6	Negative feeling frequency	8.87 (.72)	5.19(.54)	4.53**	8.9 (6.3)	5.33 (.43)	4.38**
7	Negative feeling intensity	14.16 (1.03)	9.12 (.88)	4.84**	13.3 (8.06)	9.21 (.78)	4.36**
8	Negative feeling strength	58.17 (5.30)	32.12 (4.04)	5.36**	50.6 (3.8)	35.39 (3.28)	5.22**
9	No. needs	1.90 (.59)	1.81 (.48)	.83	2.3 (.48)	1.94 (.49)	.01
10	Need frequency	6.90 (.47)	6.87 (2.3)	.09	7.6 (2.9)	7.90 (2.60)	.08
11	Need intensity	12.67 (.75)	12.77 (3.45)	.73	14.7 (4.1)	13.42 (3.59)	1.15
12	Need strength	46.67 (3.55)	49.48 (17.54)	1.14	49.5 (2.3)	55.33 (22.53)	.75
13	Need efficacy	12.09 (.79)	13.48 (3.77)	1.63	12.3 (6.0)	14.18 (3.14)	.41
14	Happy	3.03 (.65)	3.64 (.48)	5.11**	3.0 (.66)	3.3 (.79)	4.42**
15	Anger	3.30 (.81)	2.74 (.63)	4.79**	3.6(.69)	2.64 (.64)	5.41**
16	Sad	3.09 (.82)	2.47 (.62)	5.79**	3.2 (.78)	2.89 (.63)	4.98**

17	Fear	2.98 (.97)	2.79 (.89)	2.83	3.3 (1.05)	2.53 (.65)	2.5
18	Excitement	3.22 (.91)	3.27 (.87)	.72	3.0 (.81)	2.85 (.93)	1.71*
19	Disgust	1.21 (.9)	1.87 (.56)	2.11*	2 (.47)	1.97 (.92)	1.0

** - shows the significance at 0.01 level

* - Shows significance at 0.05 level

Table 4.6, Showing the t- test results of difference scores before and after the positive asset search intervention among the experimental group and control group

Sl No	Variables	Visually Impaired			Non-Visually Impaired		
		Expt (N=31)	Control (N=10)	t- value	Expt (N=33)	Control (N=11)	t- value
		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
1	No, positive feeling	.87 (.25)	.07 (.04)	1.92*	.74 (.31)	.12 (.04)	1.86*
2	No, negative feeling	-1.61 (.18)	.09 (.07)	1.72*	.94 (.52)	.21 (.05)	1.96*
3	Positive feeling frequency	3.55 (2.17)	.05)	2.01*	2.65(.69)	.53 (.15)	1.85*
4	Positive feeling intensity	6.03 (.13)	2.42 (.42)	2.46**	3.37 (.48)	.34 (.13)	1.69*
5	Positive feeling strength	21.33 (.91)	11.53 (1.24)	2.01*	22.55(.46)	-.4 (.09)	4.74**
6	Negative feeling frequency	-3.68 (.18)	.1 (.01)	1.81*	-3.3 (1.35)	.97 (.42)	3.02**
7	Negative feeling intensity	-5.04 (.15)	-.3 (.27)	3.76**	4.0 (.15)	2.68 (2.42)	2.37**
8	Negative feeling strength	-26.05 (1.26)	9.04 (.1)	3.26**	-26.05 (.52)	1.58 (.97)	1.69*
9	No. needs	.09 (.07)	.1 (.08)	.05	-.36 (.03)	.21 (.09)	.42
10	Need frequency	.13 (.09)	.11 (.07)	.52	.07 (.6)	.04 (.01)	.24
11	Need intensity	.26 (.14)	.53 (.34)	.27	-1.28 (.51)	-.93 (.63)	.52
12	Need strength	3.49 (1.43)	2.78 (1.52)	.58	-1.28 (.51)	-1.1 (.68)	.51
13	Need efficacy	1.49 (.89)	.79 (.36)	1.23	1.88 (.91)	1.24 (.97)	.68
14	Happy	.61 (.17)	.32 (.24)	1.64	.3 (.19)	.13 (.92)	1.58
15	Anger	-1.41 (.18)	.87 (.23)	1.69*	-.96 (.03)	.31 (.08)	1.69*
16	Sad	-.92 (.20)	1.1 (.87)	.94	-.31 (.15)	.32 (.07)	.04
17	Fear	-.19 (.08)	.73 (.67)	.99	.77 (.40)	.62 (.14)	.78
18	Excitement	.05 (.03)	.74 (.46)	1.24	-.15 (.08)	.06 (.02)	.07
19	Disgust	.02 (.01)	.64 (.56)	.52	-.03 (.02)	.04 (.03)	.08

** - Showing significance at 0.01 level

* - Showing significance at 0.05 level

Table 4.7, Showing the independent t-test results of experimental group and control group after the intervention

Sl. No	Variables	Visually Impaired			Non-Visually Impaired		
		Expt (N=31)	Control (N=10)	t- value	Expt (N=33)	Control (N=11)	t- value
		Mean& SD	Mean& SD		Mean& SD	Mean& SD	
1	No, positive feeling	2.22 (.92)	1.41 (.82)	2.49*	1.87 (.99)	2.01 (1.00)	2.19*
2	No, negative feeling	1.30 (.71)	2.20 (1.45)	2.65*	1.37 (.63)	3.20 (1.30)	6.09**
3	Positive feeling frequency	7.22 (.42)	3.3 (1.8)	4.77**	6.18 (.51)	5.1 (2.7)	1.12
4	Positive feeling intensity	15.83 (1.15)	23.6 (4.68)	4.92**	13.03 (1.24)	14.4 (8.0)	1.91*
5	Positive feeling strength	54.0 (3.296)	21.9 (1.95)	4.76**	44.15 (1.91)	37.6 (2.29)	1.84*
6	Negative feeling frequency	5.19(.54)	8.9 (6.3)	2.5*	5.33 (.43)	12.8 (4.77)	2.21*
7	Negative feeling intensity	9.12 (.88)	13.0 (7.78)	1.86*	9.21 (.78)	21.7 (8.09)	2.47*
8	Negative feeling strength	32.12 (4.04)	0.5 (3.8)	1.89*	35.39 (3.28)	90.8 (3.6)	5.11**
9	No. needs	1.81 (.48)	2.0 (.47)	1.11	1.94 (.49)	2.2 (.63)	1.12
10	Need frequency	6.87 (2.3)	7.0 (2.9)	.14	7.90 (2.60)	9.3 (3.56)	1.17
11	Need intensity	12.77 (3.45)	14.5 (4.14)	1.31	13.42 (3.59)	14.9 (5.38)	.37

12	Need strength	49.48 (17.54)	49.6 (2.3)	.08	55.33 (22.53)	69.7 (3.3)	1.03
13	Need efficacy	13.48 (3.77)	11.6 (5.5)	1.09	14.18 (3.14)	12.7 (3.9)	.87
14	Happy	3.64 (.48)	2.9 (.73)	3.69**	3.3 (.79)	2.8 (.68)	1.84*
15	Anger	2.74 (.63)	3.5 (.52)	3.43**	2.64 (.64)	3.1 (.73)	2.34**
16	Sad	2.47 (.62)	2.5 (.52)	.15	2.89 (.63)	3.1 (.56)	1.03
17	Fear	2.79 (.89)	3.3 (1.1)	1.5	2.53 (.65)	2.5 (.71)	.07
18	Excitement	3.27 (.87)	2.9 (.74)	1.22	2.85 (.93)	2.8 (.63)	.67
19	Disgust	1.87 (.56)	2 (.47)	.66	1.97 (.92)	2 (.47)	.41
20	Participant Satisfaction	8.91 (.63)	5.2 (.91)	14.37**	8.69 (.86)	4.1 (1.05)	12.38**

** - Showing significance at 0.01 level

* - Showing significance at 0.05 level

Table, 4.8, Showing the t-test results of independent t-test among visually impaired and non-visually impaired after the intervention

Sl. No	Variables	Experimental Group			Control Group		
		Visually Impaired (N=31)	Non-Visually Impaired (N=33)	t-value	Visually Impaired (N=10)	Non-Visually Impaired (N=11)	t-value
		Mean & SD	Mean & sd		Mean & SD	Mean & SD	
1	No, positive feeling	2.22 (.92)	1.87 (.99)	1.45	1.41 (.82)	2.01 (1.00)	1.02
2	No, negative feeling	1.30 (.71)	1.37 (.63)	.39	2.20 (1.45)	3.20 (1.30)	1.01
3	Positive feeling frequency	7.22 (.42)	6.18 (.51)	2.06*	3.3 (1.8)	5.1 (2.7)	.87
4	Positive feeling intensity	15.83 (1.15)	13.03 (1.24)	1.65	23.6 (4.68)	14.4 (8.0)	2.06*
5	Positive feeling strength	54.0 (3.296)	44.15 (1.91)	2.65*	21.9 (1.95)	37.6 (2.29)	.71
6	Negative feeling frequency	5.19(.54)	5.33 (.43)	.20	8.9 (6.3)	12.8 (4.77)	1.28
7	Negative feeling intensity	9.12 (.88)	9.21 (.78)	.07	13.0 (7.78)	21.7 (8.09)	1.56
8	Negative feeling strength	32.12 (4.04)	35.39 (3.28)	.63	0.5 (3.8)	90.8 (3.6)	2.34*
9	No. needs	1.81 (.48)	1.94 (.49)	.72	2.0 (.47)	2.2 (.63)	1.79
10	Need frequency	6.87 (2.3)	7.90 (2.60)	1.69	7.0 (2.9)	9.3 (3.56)	.98
11	Need intensity	12.77 (3.45)	13.42 (3.59)	.73	14.5 (4.14)	14.9 (5.38)	.22
12	Need strength	49.48 (17.54)	55.33 (22.53)	1.15	49.6 (2.3)	69.7 (3.3)	1.14
13	Need efficacy	13.48 (3.77)	14.18 (3.14)	.81	11.6 (5.5)	12.7 (3.9)	.66
14	Happy	3.64 (.48)	3.3 (.79)	2.06*	2.9 (.73)	2.8 (.68)	.27
15	Anger	2.74 (.63)	2.64 (.64)	.66	3.5 (.52)	3.1 (.73)	1.11
16	Sad	2.47 (.62)	2.89 (.63)	2.72*	2.5 (.52)	3.1 (.56)	1.96*
17	Fear	2.79 (.89)	2.53 (.65)	1.34	3.3 (1.1)	2.5 (.71)	1.91*
18	Excitement	3.27 (.87)	2.85 (.93)	1.89*	2.9 (.74)	2.8 (.63)	.78
19	Disgust	1.87 (.56)	1.97 (.92)	.51	2 (.47)	2 (.47)	.40
20	Participant Satisfaction	8.91 (.63)	8.69 (.86)	1.35	5.2 (.91)	4.1 (1.05)	1.78*

** - Showing significance at 0.01 level

* - Showing significance at 0.05 level

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